

EFFECT OF VOIDS ON INITIAL FAILURE OF CFRP LAMINATES

S. Aratama^{1*,2}, Y. Tsumura², M. Nishikawa², M. Hojo²

¹ Aerospace Company, Kawasaki Heavy Industries, Ltd., Kakamigahara, Japan

² Department of Mechanical Engineering and Science, Kyoto University, Kyoto, Japan,

* Corresponding author (aratama_shigeki@khi.co.jp)

Keywords: *void, transverse crack, microscopic strain, image analysis*

1 Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is inhomogeneous material consists of carbon fibers and polymeric resin matrices having strongly anisotropic material properties, such as higher tensile strength and modulus in fiber direction than those in transverse directions. Therefore, CFRP is usually used in the form of laminate fabricated by stacking prepregs in a pre-determined arrangement that includes multiple fiber directions and results in having intended material properties as a laminated part.

Similarly to the material properties, the fracture of CFRP is very complex compared to that of metallic materials that are usually treated as homogeneous and isotropic. Even in the case of a simple unidirectional laminate, fracture modes of the laminate strongly depend on the loading conditions with respect to the fiber directions.

In the case of a CFRP laminate having multiple layers and subjected to tensile or bending loads, for example, the matrix cracking in transverse direction to the loading direction called as “transverse crack” typically occurs as an initial failure of the laminate mostly in the layers of which fiber directions are transverse to the tensile stress direction [1].

This transverse crack is a fracture in resin between fibers or in interface between resin and fiber. The macroscopic strain level at the first transverse cracking is around 0.2% to 1% that is much lower than those of matrix resins that are around 5% for thermoset resins and 100% for thermoplastic resins. Since fibers in resin have very high stiffness compared to the resin itself and cause local strain concentration in the resin near the fibers, the transverse cracking usually starts at lower macroscopic strain level [2]. Such transverse cracks can cause delamination between laminate layers or fiber breakage of other layers, and finally can degrade the life of the product or result in final fracture of the product.

Fabrication of a CFRP laminate is usually performed using an autoclave to apply elevated temperature and pressure conditions in autoclave that are specified for the material system to cure the resin matrix. Temperature condition is to control the chemical reactions of the matrix resin. Pressure condition is to squeeze out excess resin, to consolidate plies, and to minimize the void content. Although the causes of void formation are understood as the moisture dissolved in resin [3] or the air entrapped during the lay-up process or during the impregnation of resin in pre-preg processing [4], many of such void formation can be eliminated by applying elevated pressure conditions in autoclave and it is possible to fabricate CFRP laminates with high internal quality. Even in the case of autoclave curing, voids may be formed if the configuration of the product is complex and the pressure conditions locally deviate from the specified ones [5]. In the case of Out-of-Autoclave curing that applies pressure conditions lower than that of autoclave curing, the process itself is prone to remain voids in laminates and a lot of research efforts are made to reduce those voids by controlling curing process conditions or reducing moistures or micro voids from the prepreg. [3, 6-9] Many of those previous researches regarding the effect of voids on the strength of CFRP laminates were focused on the relationship between void volume fraction, V_v , and the strength in each fracture modes. Those researches revealed that voids affect the mechanical properties of CFRP laminates, such as modulus of elasticity and fracture toughness and degrade compressive strength in fiber direction, tensile and compressive strength in transverse direction, and flexure strength, and interlaminar shear strength [10-16]. It has been also demonstrated that the effect of void on these strength reduction is increased in accordance with increase in V_v . Thus, although these researches investigated the effect of voids on the strength of CFRP laminate in relation to the void volume fractions, V_v , those effects in relation to the fracture mechanism from

microscopic viewpoint, in particular, the transverse cracking as the initial failure of CFRP laminates has not been well understood. Moreover, while some efforts have been made to calculate the microscopic strain field that affect the initiation of damage in CFRP laminates [17], the actual measurement has been made only to obtain the strain field [18] but not discussed in detail with respect to the initial failure of the CFRP laminates.

In this study, the effect of voids on the transverse cracking as an initial failure of CFRP laminates has been investigated to clarify the mechanism of the strength reduction in CFRP laminates containing voids caused by changed curing pressure conditions. In addition, the strain distribution in CFRP laminate layers were actually measured and evaluated in the same scale range as voids, i.e. micrometer order, because the initiations of transverse cracks are strongly affected by the microscopic mechanics.

2 Experiments

2.1 Materials and specimens

It is difficult to observe the initial failure sequences in transverse tensile test using CFRP laminate specimens consist of only 90° layers since transverse cracks in such CFRP laminates propagate instantly through the 90° layers – the layers whose fiber direction is transverse to the loading direction – and result in final failure just after their initiation.

Hobbiebrunken, et al performed 3-point bending test in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) using specimens of special stacking sequence that consists of many 0° layers between a few 90° layers on the surfaces in order to perform in-situ observation of the failure initiation in the 90° layers on the tensile side surface at the longitudinal center area of the specimens. Figs.1 and 2 show the geometry of specimens and the outline of the loading apparatus, respectively, used in these experiments [19]. This method has an advantage that enables observation of the initial failure in transverse loading condition by preventing sudden final failure of specimens by supporting most of the applied load by 0° layers and limiting the displacement of the specimens.

The same method was applied in this study. The effect of voids on the initial failure, i.e. the initiation of transverse cracks, in 90° layers using specimens of various void volume fractions, V_v . The same loading apparatus shown in Fig.2 was used. Unidirectional carbon/epoxy UTS50/#135 prepreg (Toho Tenax, 180°C cure type) was used to fabricate CFRP laminates of $[90_2/0_5]_s$ stacking sequence by

autoclave curing process. The pressure conditions in the laminate fabrication were changed from the ones specified for this material system to prepare the laminates for the specimens of three void volume fractions named Specimen A, B and C. Ultrasonic inspection was performed to check if voids are uniformly distributed in those laminates. The void volume fractions of the laminates for Specimen A, B and C were evaluated by optical microscope observation on representative cut surfaces as, 0%, 2% and 4.6%, respectively. Each piece of the specimens was cut from the corresponding laminate into the dimensions shown in Fig.1. The in-situ 3-point bending tests in SEM were performed using these specimens to observe the transverses cracking in 90° layers at the tensile side surface of these specimens. The changes in the strains at the time of transverse cracking and the crack locations and paths were evaluated.

Figs.3 and 4 show the cross sections of Specimen A and B, respectively, before in-situ 3-point bending testing. While no voids are found in Fig.3 ($V_v=0\%$), some voids were observed in Fig.4 ($V_v=4.6\%$). Since the void sizes are small enough relative to the sizes of laminate cross-sections and the distributions of voids can be assumed as random, the void volume fractions were estimated as the ratio of the cross-sectional area of the laminate to the accumulated cross-sectional area of voids measured from these SEM pictures. The shape of voids are observed as long and thin in 0° layers whose lengths are ranging from tens to hundreds micrometers and small circular or ellipse shape in 90° layers. Based on such observations, it is considered that the voids are contained in the form of circular or elliptical cylinder in CFRP layers. Moreover, resin rich regions are observed at the both ends of the voids so that voids can exist inside of the resin rich regions even if voids cannot be identified in the surface observation by SEM.

The surface of each test specimen for SEM observation was prepared by three steps of mirror polish, flattening, intermediate and final polishing using polisher (ECOMET3, BUEHLER), and 30-second gold deposition applied by an ion coater (FINECOATER JFC-1200, Japan Electron Optics Laboratory (JEOL)).

2.2 In-situ failure observation

At first, in-situ observation of the transverse crack initiation was performed. The outline of specimens and the loading apparatus were as shown in Figs.1

and 2, and the diameters of loading pin and supporting pins were 6mm and the distances between those pins were 10mm. This loading apparatus was exactly identical one shown in Fig.2, and installed in the SEM (JSM-6510, JEOL). 3-point bending load was applied by manually controlled displacement of the pins.

Through-the-thickness cracks transverse to the local tensile stress in the two 90° layers at the tensile side of specimens was defined as “transverse crack” in this test, the first transverse crack as “initial failure”, the applied force F just before the initial failure as “initial failure load”, and the macroscopic longitudinal strain ε_{22} at the center of the surface at tensile side as “initial failure strain”.

The in-situ SEM observation was performed with the magnification of 300 times, and the loads and the locations of initial failure were recorded. The applied loads were measured using a load cell with a capacity of 2kN and recorded at the times when the first two or three cracks were observed. The load cell was connected to a signal conditioner (CDV-700A, Kyowa Electronic Instruments), and the voltage output was recorded using data acquisition software (PCD-320A, Kyowa Electronic Instruments). Those obtained loads corresponding to the respective void volume fractions were compared to investigate the effects of voids.

The transverse crack locations were measured as the longitudinal distances from the location of center pin to the transverse cracks using the built-in length-measurement function of the SEM. In this study, the initial failure strains were calculated from the initial failure loads and the initial failure locations using classical laminate plate theory and beam theory with the assumption of $V_f=0.60$.

2.3 Microscopic strain measurement

To investigate the effects of microscopic inhomogeneity like voids on the transverse cracking of CFRP laminates, microscopic strain distributions in 90° layers were measured by image analysis of the SEM pictures. Since application of random patterns that is usually applied to the specimens for the strain measurement by image analysis was difficult at microscopic scale appropriate for the area around voids, fiber image itself was used instead of the random pattern since gray level difference between fiber and matrix in SEM pictures is clear to identify fibers. The in-situ 3-point bending test was performed in the same way as described in the previous section using the specimens of three levels

of void volume fractions A, B and C. SEM pictures of 5 locations of each specimen were taken at every 50N load-increasing step. The magnifications were 300 times and the picture sizes were 5120pixels by 3840pixels. To minimize the error in image analysis, attention was paid for each picture to be in focus and to include the same area for five locations as much as possible for each specimen. The image analysis program for searching fiber locations prepared for this research was used to calculate the fiber displacements and the resultant strain distributions. It was assumed that the shape of cross-sectional area of a fiber is true circle and not deformed since the modulus of elasticity of fiber is much higher than that of matrix and hence corresponding strain in fiber is negligible. Since the strains of the elements having contact with the outer circumference of the SEM pictures cannot be defined with this method, the strains ε_{22} were indicated as 0 in displaying the microscopic strain distribution.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 In-situ failure observation

The sequence of the failure events observed in the in-situ 3-point bending tests were the same for all specimens as follows;

- (1) Transverse cracking in 90° layers located near the loading point in tensile side,
- (2) Local fiber breakage in 0° layers located near the transverse cracks and,
- (3) Kink formation in 0° layers located near the loading point in compressive side.

The events (1) and (2) occurred almost at the same time and the event (3) occurred after them. The number of transverse cracks mentioned in (1) was increased with increasing in the applied load. It was also observed that some transverse cracks went through the voids while some went through the resin rich area. Based on these observations, it was considered that similar strain concentration occurred in both regions around voids and resin rich area.

The strains at transverse cracking in three point bending experiments are shown in Fig.5. These initial failure strains at the first transverse crack initiation of Specimens B and C were 68% and 50%, respectively, of those of Specimen A. Thus it was confirmed that the void volume fractions, V_v , significantly affect the initiation of transverse cracks. This tendency of reducing transverse strengths, i.e. the initial failure strains, with increasing in void volume fractions, V_v , was the same as the ones observed in the previous studies [11,12]. The ratios

of strength reductions in this Fig.5 were, however, much larger than those found in the previous studies. Fig.6 shows the initial failure of the Specimen C ($V_v=4.6\%$) as an example of transverse cracking with respect to the void locations. This transverse crack was initiated at $\varepsilon_{22}=0.59\%$ in such a way as to run through the voids located in the 90° layers, between the 0° and 90° layers and on the laminate surface. The crack was initiated in a very short instance so that it was difficult to identify its origination. This tendency about the transverse cracks to run through the voids selectively was observed in several specimens of Specimen B and C. Moreover, this tendency about the transverse cracks to run through the resin rich areas selectively was also observed in several specimens of Specimen B and C. According to this tendency, it was considered that voids exist inside of the resin rich areas found in these specimens as mentioned in 2.1.

Based on these observations, it was suggested that voids affect the microscopic strain field within the CFRP laminates and corresponding initial crack initiation. The microscopic strain field measurement was therefore planned in the next section to evaluate the effect of voids on initial failure quantitatively.

3.2 Microscopic strain measurement

Figs.8 and 10 are the results of microscopic strain measurement by image analysis of the SEM pictures shown in Fig.7 for Specimen A and Fig.9 for Specimen C, respectively. Strain distributions shown in (a) through (e) in each strain measurement results correspond to (a) through (e) in each of the original SEM pictures.

3.2.1 Strain distribution without voids

Fig.8 shows the distribution of the strain ε_{22} at $F=1.5 \times 10^2 \text{N}$ of Specimen A. Since the strains ε_{lam} , theoretically calculated values of ε_{22} at the locations between the two 90° layers at the tensile side, was 0.28% to 0.29% , it was confirmed that the strains ε_{22} were well captured by this measurement as a whole and there were some distribution in ε_{22} because of the microscopic inhomogeneity, such as the fiber locations and resin rich regions, even in the case of laminates without voids.

3.2.2. Strain distribution with voids

Fig.10 shows the distribution of the strain ε_{22} at $F=2.0 \times 10^2 \text{N}$ of Specimen C. It was confirmed that the strains ε_{22} were very high at the locations around the defects on the laminate surface or around the

voids. In particular, higher strains were observed around the voids located near to the specimen surface since the macroscopic strains ε_{22} are originally higher and the strain concentration occurs around the voids. Thus the location of the voids relative to the laminate surface can affect the initiation of initial failure.

Figs.11 through 13 show the comparison of the thickness wise distributions of void widths, w , void heights, h , and void distances from the laminate surface, d , respectively, between Specimen B and C. Since it was understood from Fig.4 that voids could exist inside of the resin rich regions even if voids cannot be identified at the surface, it was identified as a void if a dent is observed in a resin rich region and its outline is clearly identified. Fig.14 shows an example of a resin rich region that was regarded and counted as a void. Although there were no clear differences between Specimen B and C in the distributions of void widths, w , and void heights, h , there was very clear difference in the distribution of void distances, d , from the laminate surface. While there was only one peak around $d=190\mu\text{m}$ for Specimen B, there were two peaks $d=70\mu\text{m}$ and $270\mu\text{m}$ for Specimen C. Since the thickness of one layer of this CFRP laminate was about $190\mu\text{m}$ and the average void width was around $30\mu\text{m}$ to $40\mu\text{m}$, it was understood that voids mainly exist in the region between the two 90° layers for Specimen B while they mainly exist in each of the two 90° layers for Specimen C.

Based on these results, the reason why the initial failure strains reduced with increasing in void volume fractions, V_v , can be explained as follows. Since the load was applied by bending and the macroscopic strain was originally higher in the region near the surface at the tensile side of the specimen, the void locations relative to the laminate surface strongly affect the strains, and higher strains were caused around the voids near to the specimen surface. Considering that many of voids exist in the region between the two 90° layers for Specimen B and in the region in each of the two 90° layers for Specimen C, Specimen C should contain more voids near to the specimen surface than Specimen B and had more effect on the reduction of the initial failure strains by strain concentration around the voids.

3.2.3. Comparison of measured strains and theoretically calculated strains

Figs.15 and 16 show the comparison of measured strains ε_{22} and their theoretically calculated values for Specimen A and C, respectively. The measured

strains were defined here as the average of ε_{22} measured in the five observation areas for each of Figs.8 and 10. The straight lines in the graphs show the case when the measured strains equals to the calculated strains.

Fig.15, $V_v=0\%$, showed good agreement between the measured strains and the calculated strains in the range of ε_{22} from 0 to 0.4%, and it was confirmed that the microscopic strain measurement method used for this test was appropriate. It was also confirmed that the material properties of 90° layers were in elastic region since the theory used for this calculation assumed elastic deformations. In the region ε_{22} is over 0.6%, the non-linear behavior that the measured strains became larger than the calculated strains showed the fact that plastic deformations started in these regions.

Fig.16, $V_v=2.0\%$, showed linear relationship between the measured strains and the calculated strains in the region up to $\varepsilon_{22}=0.5\%$. However, since the measured strains were slightly larger than the calculated strains, the stiffness of Specimen B was considered to be a little lower than the stiffness theoretically assumed in calculation.

Fig.17, $V_v=4.6\%$, also showed good agreement between the measured strains and the calculated strains in the range of ε_{22} from 0 to 0.4%, and the non-linear behavior that the measured strains became larger than the calculated strains in the region ε_{22} is just over 0.4%. This fact showed that plastic deformations of Specimen C started earlier than that of Specimen A.

It was confirmed from these results that the stiffness reduction and plastic deformation of resin started earlier when voids are included in CFRP laminates. The latter result, in particular, can be the reason why the macroscopic failure strains for Specimen B and C in the in-situ 3-point bending test were much lower than those for Specimen A.

In the present study, it should be noted that creeping effect would be negligible according to the previous study [20], even though the testing time for one specimen could be some hours to apply loads on step-by-step basis and take SEM pictures at every loading step.

4 Conclusions

The initial failure behavior of 90° layers in CFRP laminates subjected to transverse loading were observed by in-situ 3-point bending test applying enforced displacement in SEM. The results confirmed that the initial failure strains actually

reduced with the increase in the void volume fractions, V_v .

It was also observed that several transverse cracks ran through the voids, and the strain concentration around the voids could affect the initiation of transverse cracks.

The microscopic strain distribution at micrometer order was performed using SEM pictures to identify the fiber locations before and during loading and calculate displacement of those fibers and resultant strains in the in-situ 3-point bending test in SEM.

The result showed the strain concentration really occurred in the regions around the voids. While there were no clear relationship between the strain concentration and the characteristics regarding the void shape, such as void width, w , and void height, h , it was showed that the strain concentration was increased in the cases that voids were located near to the laminate surface.

In addition to clarify the effect of voids caused by changed curing pressure conditions on the transverse crack initiation in CFRP cross-ply laminates, it was considered that plastic deformation of resin started much earlier in the laminate including voids than in the laminate without voids at lower macroscopic strain, and damage in resin in these regions was caused and resulted in the transverse strength reduction.

Based on the result obtained in this study, it is necessary to account for not only the effect of void volume fractions, V_v , but also the effect of geometric arrangement of void with respect to the distance to the laminate surface.

In addition, even though the microscopic strain measurement using SEM pictures taken during in-situ 3-point bending test provided a lot of important information about the actual behavior of the specimens, the observation was only of the surface conditions and did not include any information about the internal conditions of the CFRP laminates, such as three dimensional strain distributions. Therefore, it is considered to be necessary to investigate the three dimensional effect of strain concentration around the voids by experiments and/or calculations in the future work.

Fig.1. Geometry of specimen.

Fig.2. Loading apparatus installed in SEM.

Fig.3. Cross section of specimen A ($V_v=0\%$).

Fig.4. Cross section of specimen B ($V_v=2.0\%$).

Fig.5. Strains at the first transverse cracking.

Fig.6. Transverse crack through voids in specimen C.

Fig.7. SEM picture of specimen A used in microscopic strain measurement.

Fig.8. Strain distribution (ϵ_{22}) in specimen A at $F=1.5 \times 10^2$ N.

Fig.9. SEM picture of specimen C used in microscopic strain measurement.

Fig.10. Strain distribution (ϵ_{22}) in specimen C at $F=2.0 \times 10^2$ N.

Fig.11. Distribution of void width, w , in specimen B and C.

Fig.12. Distribution of void height, h , in specimen B and C.

Fig.13. Distribution of distances from void to laminate surface, d , in specimen B and C.

Fig.14. Definitions of void width, w , void height, h , and distances from void to laminate surface, d , for a resin rich region regarded as a void.

Fig.15. Relationship between measured strain and calculated strain - specimen A.

Fig.16. Relationship between measured strain and calculated strain - specimen B.

Fig.17. Relationship between measured strain and calculated strain - specimen C.

References

- [1] D. Hull and T. W. Clyne. "An introduction to composite materials". 2nd edition, Cambridge University Press, 1996.
- [2] J. M. M. De Kok, H. E. H. Meijer and A. A. J. M. Peijs. "The influence of matrix plasticity on the failure strain of transversely loaded composite materials". *Proceedings of ICCM 9*, Madrid, Spain, pp. 242-249, 1993.
- [3] L. K. Grunenfelder and S. R. Nutt. "Void formation in composite prepregs - effect of dissolved moisture". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 70, pp. 2304-2309, 2010.
- [4] S. S. Tavares, V. Michaud & J.-A. E. Månson, "Through thickness air permeability of prepregs during cure". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 40, pp. 1587-1596, 2009.
- [5] J. M. Tang, W. I. Lee and G. S. Springer. "Effects of Cure Pressure on Resin Flow, Voids, and Mechanical Properties". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 21, pp. 421-440, 1987.
- [6] L. K. Grunenfelder & S. R. Nutt, "Out-time effects on VBO (vacuum bag only) prepreg and laminate properties". *SAMPE Journal*, Vol. 47, No. 5, pp. 6-13, 2011.
- [7] L. W. Davies, R. J. Day, D. Bond, A. Nesbitt, J. Ellis and E. Gardon. "Effect of cure cycle heat transfer rates on the physical and mechanical properties of an epoxy matrix composite". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 67, pp. 1892-1899, 2007.
- [8] T. Centea and P. Hubert. "Modelling the effect of material properties and process parameters on tow impregnation in out-of-autoclave prepregs". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 43, pp. 1505-1513, 2012.
- [9] J. C. Hughes, N. Arai, A. P. Haro and J. A. Satterwhite. "Studies for the development of OOA prepreg used in aircraft applications". *Proceedings of SAMPE Tech 2011*, Fort Worth, Texas, U.S.A., October 2011.
- [10] B. D. Harper, G. H. Staab and R. S. Chen. "A note on the effects of voids upon the hygral and mechanical properties of AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 21, pp. 280-289, 1987.
- [11] P. Olivier, J. P. Cottu and B. Ferret. "Effects of cure cycle pressure and voids on some mechanical properties of carbon/epoxy laminates". *Composites*, Vol. 26, No. 7, pp. 509-515, 1995.
- [12] L. Ye, K. Friedrich, J. Kästel and Y.-W. Mai. "Consolidation of unidirectional CF/PEEK composites from commingled yarn prepreg". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 54, pp. 349-358, 1995.
- [13] N. L. Hancox. "The compression strength of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced plastic". *Journal of materials science*, Vol. 10, pp. 234-242, 1975.
- [14] N. L. Hancox. "The effects of flaws and voids on the shear properties of CFRP". *Journal of materials science*, Vol. 12, pp. 884-892, 1977.
- [15] S. Hernández, F. Sket, J. M. Molina-Aldareguía, C. González and J. LLorca. "Effect of curing cycle on void distribution and interlaminar shear strength in polymer-matrix composites". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 71, pp. 1331-1341, 2011.
- [16] R. Talreja and C. V. Singh. "Damage and Failure of Composite Materials", Cambridge University Press, 2012.

- [17] T. Okabe, M. Nishikawa and H. Toyoshima. "A periodic unit-cell simulation of fiber arrangement dependence on the transverse tensile failure in unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced composites". *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 48, pp. 2948-2959, 2011.
- [18] L. P. Canal, C. González, J.M. Molina-Aldareguía, J. Segrado and J. LLorca. "Application of digital image correlation at the microscale in fiber-reinforced composites". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 43, pp. 1630-1638, 2012.
- [19] T. Hobbiebrunken, M. Hojo, T. Adachi, C. De Jong and B. Fiedler. "Evaluation of interfacial strength in CF/epoxies using FEM and in-situ experiments". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 37, pp. 2248-2256, 2006.
- [20] J. Raghavan and M. Meshii. "Creep of polymer composites". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 57, pp. 1673-1688, 1997.